

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of Some Fluorine Containing *N*-Acyl-arylsulphonamides

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Several *N*-acyl derivatives of 3,4-dichlorobenzene-sulphonamide have been offered by J. R. Geigy as insecticides¹. Fluorine-containing *N*-sulphanilylbenzamides have been reported in literature². It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise and evaluate the pesticidal properties of the title compounds as similar compounds do not seem to have been studied so far. The compounds have been prepared by the action of appropriate acid chloride on substituted arylsulphonamide in benzene solution³ and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
N-Acyl-1-arylsulphonamides.
Ar.SO₂NHCOR.

No.	Ar.	R.	M.P.	Yield	Formula	% Sulphur.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	2-Bromo-5-fluoro-P	CH ₃	134-35°	61%	C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ NBrFS	10.52	10.81
2	4-Fluoro-P	CH ₂ Cl	78-79°	69	C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ NClFS	11.96	12.72
3	2-Methyl-5-fluoro-P	CH ₂ Cl	94-95°	60.4	C ₉ H ₉ O ₃ NClFS	11.18	12.05
4	4-Fluoro-P	<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₅	100-102°	58	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃ NFS	10.74	10.63
5	2,5-Dichloro-P	4-F-C ₆ H ₄	222-23°	52	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃ NCl ₂ FS	9.28	9.19
6	2,5-Dibromo-P	4-F-C ₆ H ₄	159-60°	63	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃ NBr ₂ FS	7.04	7.32
7	4-Methyl-P	4-F-C ₆ H ₄	93-94°	49	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ NFS	10.86	11.30
8	4-Chloro-P	4-F-C ₆ H ₄	135-36°	57	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ NClFS	10.44	10.20
9	4-Fluoronaphthyl	CH ₂ Br	112-14°	53	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ NBrFS	10.02	9.25
10	2-Methyl-5-fluoro-P	<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₁₅	90-91°	50	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃ NFS	9.47	10.16

Note: P denotes phenyl.

*General Method of Preparation*⁴.—A mixture of arylsulphonamide (2*M*), appropriate acid chloride (1*M*), and copper powder (0.5 g.) in benzene (35 ml) was refluxed for 4 to 5 hours. After removal of benzene, the *N*-acylarylsulphonamide was isolated in the usual way.

The pesticidal properties of the compounds will be communicated in due course.

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1. Swiss. Pat., 224846/1943.
2. *Chem. Abst.*, 1958, 62, 17166.
3. *Ibid.*, 1949, 43, 2231
4. Joshi and Giri, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 117.